

In Vitro Anti-Oxidant Activity and Anti-Cholinesterase of *Clerodendrum Serratum* Flowers and Leaves

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder clinically characterized by loss of memory and cognition. Cholinergic deficit and oxidative stress have been implicated in the pathogenesis of AD. Therefore, inhibition of acetylcholinesterase and oxidation are the two promising strategies in the development of drug for AD. In the present study, the antioxidant potential and neuroprotective activity of ethanolic extracts of flowers and leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* were assessed DPPH (2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl), hydroxyl and 2, 2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS) radical scavenging capacity. In addition, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitory activity were performed using Ellman's method. Results obtained from the study clearly demonstrates that ethanolic extracts of flowers and leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* has shown promising anti-oxidant and acetylcholinesterase inhibition.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease; *Clerodendrum serratum*; acetylcholinesterase; antioxidant

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by cognitive decline, memory loss, and behavioral changes. It poses a significant burden on individuals, families, and healthcare systems worldwide. Despite decades of research, the exact etiology of AD remains elusive, though it is believed to involve complex interactions between genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors. Currently, available treatments for AD focus on symptomatic management and include acetylcholinesterase inhibitors and N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonists. Although not fully understood, the "cholinergic hypothesis" proposes that the neurodegenerative mechanism is a decline of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine in the brain. The drugs presently used to treat AD patients act as enhancers of the acetylcholine level in the brain, responsible for central cholinergic transmission. After being delivered across neuronal synapses, acetylcholine is hydrolyzed to a choline and an acetyl group by the enzyme acetylcholinesterase. Therefore, applying inhibitors of acetylcholinesterase,

acetylcholine is not hydrolyzed, maintaining its activity as a neurotransmitter. However, some of the drugs approved for the treatment of AD symptoms show hepatotoxicity, higher risk of urinary incontinence, increased risk of bradycardia and other cardiovascular adverse effects, pulmonary disorders, and involuntary weight loss, and the search continues for new drugs that are more efficient in brain penetration, less harmful, and with high bioavailability. [1]

The acetylcholinesterase enzyme (AChE) is an attractive target for the discovery of mechanism-based inhibitors because of its role in hydrolysis of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. AChE inhibitors as rivastigmine, donepezil, or galantamine are currently the most effective agents to treat cognitive symptoms of AD and have other possible therapeutic applications in the treatment of other neurodegenerative disorders. Recently, research on prevention and treatment of Alzheimer has focused on naturally occurring acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors from plants, namely, polyphenolic compounds such as flavonoids with inhibitory

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capacity similar to that of the currently prescribed AChE inhibitor drugs, of which the alkaloid galantamine is a perfect example. This compound offers the advantage of being better tolerated and cheaper, since it is commonly found in foods, and its antioxidant activity and strong metal chelator capability may also contribute to the decrease of the oxidative stress that affects tissues associated with Alzheimer's disease. [2]

Clerodendrum serratum Linn. (Family: Verbenaceae) is very widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. Ethno-medicinal importance of the plant has been reported in various indigenous systems of medicines like Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani for the treatment of various life-threatening diseases such as syphilis, typhoid, cancer, jaundice and hypertension. Some of the chief constituents found in the plant are D-mannitol, hispidulin, cleroflavone, apigenin, scutellarein, serratagenic acid, acteoside, verbascoside, oleanolic acid, clerodermic acid, γ -sitosterol, β -sitosterol, cholestanol, clerosterol, campesterol and 24-ethyl cholesterol. Traditionally, it has been also used as anti-rheumatic, anti-asthmatic, febrifuge, in cephalalgia and ophthalmia. The roots of *Clerodendrum serratum* are also used as anti-oxidant, anti-bacterial, and anti-fungal. Besides these the antimicrobial value of this herbal plant has also been reported in its stems and leaves. The aim of this study is to investigate possible acetylcholinesterase inhibition and Antioxidant activity of ethanolic extracts flowers and leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* in order to point out the role of these plant as potential sources for the development of therapeutic agents for AD. [3]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Material and Preparation of extract:

The fresh flowers and leaves of the young and matured plants *Clerodendrum serratum* belonging to the family Verbenaceae were collected in bulk. The *Clerodendrum serratum* leaves and flowers was taxonomically identified and authenticated and a voucher of aerial root specimen has been deposited at the department herbarium of Jayamukhi College of Pharmacy. The flowers and leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* were shade dried. The dried plant material

was pulverized in an electrical processor and then the powder was separated. 50 gram of dried powder material was extracted in a soxhlet apparatus with 200 ml. of absolute alcohol. The ethanolic extract was then distilled, evaporated and dried in vacuum. After collection, leaves and flowers were washed separately very carefully and clearly with water and dried under shade.

Determination of Antioxidant Activity by Scavenging Effect on 2, 2'-diphenyl-1-picryl Hydrazyl Radical (DPPH):

Various concentrations of different extracts of *Clerodendrum serratum* (0.5 ml each) were mixed thoroughly with 1-ml methanol solution of 0.1 mM DPPH. The mixture was allowed to stand for 30 min in the dark. The absorbance was measured at 523 nm using a UV/VIS Spectrophotometer. An equal amount of DPPH and methanol were used as standard and blank, respectively. The scavenging activity was calculated using the following formula: [4]

$$\text{Scavenging (\%)} = (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}} \times 100,$$

where A_{sample} is the absorbance of the test sample and A_{control} is the absorbance of the control.

Determination of Antioxidant Activity by Hydroxyl radical scavenging effect:

The assay is based on quantification of the degradation product of 2-deoxyribose by condensation with TBA. Hydroxyl radical was generated by the Fe^{3+} -ascorbate-EDTA- H_2O_2 system (the Fenton reaction). The reaction mixture contained, in a final volume of 1 ml, 2-deoxy-2-ribose (2.8 mM); KH_2PO_4 -KOH buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4); FeCl_3 (100 μM); EDTA (100 μM); H_2O_2 (1.0 mM); ascorbic acid (100 μM) and various concentrations (0–200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of the test sample or reference compound. After incubation for 1 h at 37°C, 0.5 ml of the reaction mixture was added to 1 ml 2.8% TCA, then 1 ml 1% aqueous TBA was added and the mixture was incubated at 90°C for 15 min to develop the color. After cooling, the absorbance was measured at 532 nm against an appropriate blank solution. All tests were performed six times. Mannitol, a classical OH. scavenger, was used as a positive control. Percentage inhibition was evaluated by comparing the test and blank solutions. [5]

Determination of Antioxidant Activity by 2, 2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS) radical scavenging activity:

The ABTS^{•+} radical cation [2, 2 Azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazolin-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt] was generated by reacting ABTS stock solution (7.0 mM) with potassium persulfate (2.45 mM) after incubation at room temperature in the dark for 16 h. For the estimation, the ABTS^{•+} solution was diluted with ethanol to an absorbance of 0.7 (\pm 0.02) at 734 nm. Sample aliquots were taken and volume was made up 1.0 ml with ethanol. 1.0 ml of diluted ABTS^{•+} solution was added and the contents were properly mixed for 10 seconds. The absorbance of the resulting oxidized solution was measured at 734 nm and compared to that of the calibrated Trolox standard. The resultant absorbance of standard as well as sample should fall between 20% - 80% inhibition of the control absorbance. [6]

The percentage inhibition of absorbance was calculated as $[(Ac - Ae)/Ac] \times 100$

where, Ac = absorbance of control; Ae = absorbance of extract.

Determination of Anti-acetylcholinesterase Activity:

The acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity was assayed following an adaptation of the spectrophotometric method reported by Ellman et al. In test tube 1710 μ L of 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer pH 8.0 and 250 μ L of plant extracts at the concentrations of 25 – 400 μ g/ mL, 10 μ L 6.67 U/mL-1 AChE and 20 μ L of 10 mM of DTNB (5,5'-dithio-bis[2-nitrobenzoic acid]) in buffer were added. Positive control namely galantamine were prepared in serial concentration as same as test extract by dissolving in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer pH 8.0. The mixture was incubated for 15 min at 37°C. Then, 10 μ L of acetylthiocholine iodide (200 mM) in buffer were added to the mixture and the absorbance was measured at 412 nm every 10 sec for 3 mins, for a blank with buffer instead of enzyme solution was used. Percentage inhibition was calculated. [7]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Alzheimer's disease, a progressive neurodegenerative disorder and the most common cause of dementia, is reaching epidemic proportions worldwide. To go along with the increase in the number of elderly people, AD is assumed to rise markedly in the coming decades. Cholinergic deficit, deposition of amyloid plaque and formation of neurofibrillary tangles, oxidative stress, and inflammation are the prominent features of AD. Although several mechanisms of AD pathogenesis have been delineated, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) still remains as the most attractive therapeutic target for symptomatic improvement of AD. Inhibition of AChE elevates the level of acetylcholine in the synaptic cleft and improves the cholinergic neurotransmission. To date, only four drugs have been approved by the FDA for treating AD, among which three are AChE inhibitors—donepezil, galantamine, and rivastigmine. Although these drugs are effective in ameliorating the memory and cognition, they cannot stop the disease progression. Mounting evidences suggest that oxidative stress is also involved in the progression of AD. Naturally occurring compounds from plants have been discovered to be potential sources of useful AChE inhibitors. [8] Mounting evidences suggest that oxidative stress is also involved in the progression of AD. It has been clearly demonstrated that Abeta protein, the major constituent of senile plaque, can increase the free radical production and reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to oxidative stress. ROS can attack most of the cell constituents including DNA, protein, and lipid, and an increased oxidation of DNA and protein and peroxidation of lipid are observed in the brain with AD. Antioxidants have been found to reduce the oxidative stress-induced damage in AD. Therefore, there is growing consensus that an agent that can modulate the multiple pathologic processes may yield a better therapeutic effect. In recent times, interest in medicinal plants for natural drug has increased significantly due to toxicity of the synthetic drugs. [9]

The extractive values of flowers and leaves extract of *Clerodendrum serratum* were calculated. The percentage yield of flowers and leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* was found to be 21.14% and 38.62% respectively. . The ethanolic extract of flowers extract of *Clerodendrum serratum* showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, proteins, amino acids, steroids, fats and oils, and

saponins; whereas the ethanolic extract of leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, proteins, amino acids, tannins, steroids, triterpenoids, fats and oils, saponins and glycosides.

DPPH radical scavenging assay:

The flowers and leaves extract of *Clerodendrum serratum* was evaluated for its ability to quench the DPPH., which is one of the few stable organic nitrogen radicals and bears a purple colour. This assay is based on the measurement of the loss of DPPH after reaction with samples. It is considered as the prior

mechanism involved in the electron transfer. [10] The IC50 value is a parameter widely used to measure the antioxidant activity of test samples. It is calculated as the concentration of antioxidants needed to decrease the initial DPPH concentration by 50%. Thus, the lower IC50 value the higher antioxidant activity. The Leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* showed an antioxidant activity (IC50 = 41.62±1.84µg/mL) comparable to the reference ascorbic acid (IC50 = 8.72 ± 0.36). The The t-test analysis showed that there is significant difference in the DPPH radical scavenging activity among the different extract of test sample and standard ascorbic acid. As shown in Table 1 and 2.

S. No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Ascorbic Acid (Standard)
1.	10	36.16±0.85	39.98±1.33	44.44±1.54
2.	20	39.77±0.84	46.24±0.89	51.79±0.91
3.	40	41.32±1.69	51.76±0.78	58.23±1.12
4.	60	44.33±0.98	59.94±0.86	67.36±0.82
5.	80	48.09±0.27	62.24±0.77	79.14±0.37
6.	100	61.22±1.04	71.98±0.63	87.16±1.09

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

S. No	Extract/Positive control	IC50 Value DPPH assay ± SD (µg /ml)
1	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	71.28±1.24
2	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	41.62±1.84
3	Ascorbic Acid (Standard)	8.72 ± 0.36

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Hydroxyl Radical Scavenging Activity:

Brain aerobic metabolism normally render hydrogen peroxide as a bi product. H2O2 is often considered a toxic molecule for a wide range of living systems. It has also been reported to be implicated in severe pathological conditions such as cancer, ischaemia and neurodegenerative diseases. Hence a drug which quenches the H2O2 radical may serves as better

therapeutic lead for the stress related disorders.[11] All the extracts were screened for H2O2 radical scavenging activity in which the highest activity was detected in Leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum*. The t-test analysis showed that there is significant difference in the H2O2 radical scavenging activity among the different concentration extract of test sample and standard Butylated hydroxyanisole shown in Table 3 and 4.

S. No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Butylated hydroxyanisole (Standard)
1.	10	9.11±0.81	15.27±0.63	22.56±1.04
2.	20	12.72±1.01	27.79±0.77	35.72±0.82
3.	40	20.54±0.66	33.82±0.66	48.62±1.93

4.	60	31.47±1.59	45.54±1.24	61.09±3.56
5.	80	39.96±1.02	52.69±0.92	68.46±2.21
6.	100	51.89±0.89	67.26±0.72	76.48±1.06

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

S. No	Extract/Positive control	IC50 Value H2O2 radical scavenging assay ± SD (µg/ml)
1	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	109.87±2.24
2	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	74.72± 2.87
3	Butylated hydroxyanisole (Standard)	16.94 ±2.33

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

ABTS. + radical scavenging activity:

The ABTS•+ chromophore is produced through the reaction between ABTS and potassium persulfate which converts ABTS into its radical cation. This radical cation is blue in color and absorbs light at 734

nm [12]. The ABTS•+ is reactive towards most antioxidants including phenols, thiols and vitamin C. The leaves extract of *Clerodendrum serratum* showed inhibition of ABTS radical production in a concentration-dependent manner shown in Table 5 and 6.

S. No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Trolox (Standard)
1.	10	09.45±1.54	11.27±3.07	11.27±3.07
2.	20	12.24±2.01	24.35±2.98	24.35±2.98
3.	40	23.76±1.82	48.62±1.93	48.62±1.93
4.	60	35.41±1.35	61.09±3.56	61.09±3.56
5.	80	42.62±1.63	68.46±2.21	68.46±2.21
6.	100	48.35±2.17	72.48±1.06	72.48±1.06

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

S. No	Extract/Positive control	IC50 Value ABTS.+ radical scavenging assay ± SD (µg/ml)
1	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	275.69 ±4.08
2	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	124.38±3.74
3	Trolox (Standard)	08.26±3.52

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Acetylcholinesterase Enzyme Inhibitory Activity:

Preventing breaking down of ACh is responsible for the elevation of ACh level in the synaptic cleft by inhibition of AChE is the most significant changes observed in AD. Experimental evidences illustrate that AChE accelerates aggregation of amyloid-beta peptide and formation of amyloid-beta-AChE complex at the synaptic region of hippocampus leading to neuronal degeneration [13]. Symptomatic

treatment for AD involves potentiation of cholinergic activity through the inhibition of AChE. Therefore, the current study was carried out to assess the AChE inhibitory activity of different extracts of *Clerodendrum serratum*. Results showed that among the Leaves of *Clerodendrum serratum* extracts showed significant AChE inhibitory activity with IC50 values of 165.6 ± 17.68, when compared with positive control (IC50 value of 42.77 ± 3.08 µg/ml) (Table 7 and 8)

Table 7: Percentage inhibition of extracts on AChE enzyme activity

S. No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	Galanthamine (Standard)
1.	25	23.54± 2.38	29.98± 2.01	38.84±1.84
2.	50	34.67± 1.06	42.97± 1.68	51.27±2.24
3.	100	38.98± 2.12	57.24± 2.26	64.38±1.67
4.	200	42.35± 1.09	59.61±1.84	71.62±1.91
5.	500	44.46± 1.77	65.59± 2.26	80.51± 1.58

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 8: IC50 Values for AChE inhibition by plant extracts and standard

S. No	Extract/Positive control	IC50 Value AChE inhibition activity ± SD (µg/ml)
1	Flowers of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	428.74 ± 6.94
2	Leaves of <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i>	185.26 ± 8.27
3	Galanthamine (Standard)	42.77 ± 3.08

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Hence the result suggests that the presence of free radical neutralization and AChE inhibition of ethanolic extract of *Clerodendrum serratum* flowers and leaves may be due to the existence of various Phytochemicals in the FB aerial root extracts.

CONCLUSION

These findings demonstrate the remarkable potential of *Clerodendrum serratum* flowers and leaves ethanolic extracts as valuable source of antioxidants with interesting acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity. Therefore, the plant has promising compounds to be tested as potential drugs for the treatment of diseases resulting from oxidative stress like AD. Due to the presence of significant antioxidant activity of this plant, further studies are underway for isolation and identification of lead compound(s) to prevent the AD and other neurodegenerative disorders.

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